

Balanitol, a New Sesquiterpene from *Balanites roxburghii*. Carbon-13 NMR Analysis of Eudesmane Sesquiterpenoids

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Balanitol $C_{15}H_{28}O_2$, a new sesquiterpene alcohol has been isolated from the bark of *Balanites roxburghii*. Its structure has shown to be 1β -hydroxy-dihydroeudesmol by chemical transformations and spectral analysis. Balanitol is accompanied by an isomeric compound, m.p. $78-79^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 27.9^\circ$. The ^{13}C NMR spectra of some eudesmane type sesquiterpenes have been analysed.

BALANITES roxburghii, Planch. (Zygophyllaceae-Balanitoideae), a tree indigenous to India, is claimed to have a selection of curative properties. Previous workers have examined leaves, fruits and roots mainly for the presence of sapogenins¹. More recently, a detailed analysis of the kernel and leaves of *B. roxburghii* has been reported². The trunk bark has not been examined to date.

B. roxburghii was thought for many years to be synonymous with *B. aegyptiaca*, but recent taxonomic observations³ suggest a difference. In *B. roxburghii* diosgenin exceeded yamogenin in all morphological parts whilst *B. aegyptiaca* yielded yamogenin from the root and fruit wall.

We undertook a phytochemical study of a sample of the trunk bark of *B. roxburghii* collected in the western part of India (Rajasthan). This report describes two new sesquiterpenes, both crystalline, isolated from the chloroform extract of the bark.

Compound **A**, m.p. $158-160^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +10.8^\circ$, for which we propose the name balanitol and structure **1**, gave elemental analyses and mass spectral data (see below) for $C_{15}H_{28}O_2$. Its IR spectrum, devoid of carbonyl absorption, showed OH bands and its 1H -NMR spectrum exhibited signals for four methyl groups (a secondary, a tertiary and two methyls of a propan-2-ol, at 0.88, 0.9 and 1.18 ppm, respectively).

The two oxygen functions of balanitol are involved in a secondary and a tertiary alcohol, since in addition to the 1H -NMR signal at 3.25 ppm (triplet) due to a $CHOH$ grouping, oxidation with Jones' reagent gave the hydroxy-ketone (**2**), $C_{15}H_{26}O_2$ ($M^+ = 238$), m.p. $101-103^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +50.5^\circ$, D.C.: $\Delta_{\epsilon_{230-270nm}} = +0.59$ and $\Delta_{\epsilon_{230-270nm}} = +0.55$. Its 1H -NMR spectrum showed the secondary methyl group at 0.95 ppm, the tertiary methyl group at 1.13 ppm and the two methyls of the propan-2-ol grouping at 1.2 ppm. The mass spectra of compounds **1** and **2** show ($M^+ - 58$) ions at m/e 182 and 180, respectively, thus confirming the presence of a $-C(OH)(CH_3)_2$ grouping.

Reduction of the tosyl hydrazone of the hydroxy-ketone (**2**) with $NaBH_4$ afforded a monoalcohol (**3**), m.p. $85-86^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +19^\circ$ which proved to be identical with dihydroeudesmol. An authentic sample of the latter was obtained from a 6:10 mixture of α -(**4**) and β -eudesmol (**5**) which was converted to 100% β -eudesmol by irradiation⁴, and this product was catalytically hydrogenated to give dihydroeudesmol (**3**) with the axially oriented methyl⁶ at position 4.

The remaining problem was to assign the position of the secondary alcohol on the dihydro eudesmol skeleton. The mass spectrum of the deuterated hydroxy-ketone showed that only two deuterium atoms have been incorporated α to the keto group. This result excludes positions 2 and 8 but not position 3 for this group, since it is known that the equatorial hydrogen at position 4 is not exchangeable in the 3-keto-4-methyl steroids⁶. From the analysis of the 1H -NMR spectrum of the hydroxyketone, it was seen that the signal for angular methyl group shifted downfield (1.13 ppm) relative to its position in the natural product (0.9 ppm). The secondary alcoholic group, therefore, is at position 1 or 9. A decision could not be made by the circular dichroism data but the following results are in favour of position 1 for the secondary hydroxyl group of balanitol. Treatment of the hydroxyketone (**2**) with ethyleneglycol in presence of *p*-toluene-sulfonic acid gave the dioxolane derivative **6** ($M^+ = 264$) in which the propan-2-ol underwent dehydration. The mass spectrum of this derivative shows a peak at m/e 99 assignable to the ion (**X**)⁷; the presence of a peak at m/e 139, corresponding to the ion (**Y**) could have been expected if the ketal grouping of compound **6** were at position 9. The mass spectrum of the dioxolane derivative displays also ions at m/e 249 ($M^+ - 15$), at m/e 202 due to loss of ethylene glycol and a subsequent strong peak at m/e 159 assignable to the ion resulting from the loss of C_3H_7 . This ion could only arise from double bond migration of an isopropylene group⁷. The presence of the ion at m/e 99 and the loss of C_3H_7 could be accounted for if the oxygen function was at position 1.

The β stereochemistry for the secondary hydroxyl group of balanitol is indicated by the W 1/2 (13 Hz)

of the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ signal at 3.25 ppm. The values of $W\ 1/2$ of the NMR signal of an equatorially oriented CHOH group are generally found⁸ between 10 and 20 Hz,

In order to prove the above conclusions and to locate the hydroxyl group of the new sesquiterpene, a ^{13}C NMR spectral analysis of balanitol (1) and of some related compounds was undertaken. Noise and off-resonance decoupled ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded for compounds 1 to 5 and the signal assignments are indicated in the Table. An inspection of the chemical shift values permits one to draw the unambiguous conclusion that the secondary hydroxyl group of balanitol is attached to C-1 with the β -equatorial configuration.

The shift assignment for dihydroeudesmol (3) is straightforward and does not require any special comment. The spectral comparison between 1 and 3 indicated a strong β -effect in the spectrum of balanitol (1) on a quaternary carbon and on a methylene signal which can be assigned respectively to C-10 and to C-2. On the other hand, upfield γ -effects are observed on the C-9 signal of 1 as a result of the *peri*-interaction between the hydroxyl at C-1 and H-9 β , as well as on the C-15 signal of 1 as a consequence of the γ -gauche steric-interaction between the hydroxyl and the methyl groups. In case of a *trans* disposition of the C-1

hydroxyl group with respect to C-15 such an upfield effect would not be expected. Furthermore, the chemical shift similarity of C-3 and C-5 of balanitol (1) and dihydroeudesmol (3) indicates that the configuration of the C-1 substituent of 1 must be equatorial.

Concerning the hydroxyketone (2), the resonance of C-9 is found upfield with respect to the corresponding carbon of compound 3 as a consequence of the eclipsing effect of the carbonyl group in the γ -position⁹. As expected, in the spectrum of the diderated ketone 2 the signal at 34.0 ppm is not observed.

The shift assignment for compounds 4 and 5 is self-explanatory.

After the completion of this work our attention was drawn to a paper by Gerber and Denney¹⁰ describing an analysis of the Carbon-13 spectra of eudesmane sesquiterpenols which include dihydroeudesmol (3). The assignments suggested by the above authors agree with our results except for the values of the chemical shifts of C-14 and C-15 which have to be reversed, i.e. 14.8 and 19.6 ppm, respectively. In balanitol (1) these two signals are found at 14.9 and 14.0 ppm, the upfield shift of C-15 in 1 is due to the presence of the hydroxyl at C-1 as already pointed out. Moreover, we consider that there is no ambiguity in assigning the chemical shifts to C-1 and C-9, i.e., 41.7 and 44.6 ppm, respectively in view of the shift contrast between the spectra of 1 and 3, C-9 of 1 must be upfield with respect to the same carbon in 3 as a result of the *peri*-effect¹¹.

Determination of the molecular weight of balanitol (1) by chemical ionisation mass spectrometry. The chemical ionisation mass spectrum of 1 using isobutane as reactant gas does not show any peak MH^+ but only displays a peak at m/e 223 ($\text{MH}-18$)⁺. This finding can be explained by the ready dehydration of the protonated (MH^+) tertiary alcohols leading to highly stable carbonium ions as shown below.

However, several technics allow the determination of the molecular weight by chemical ionisation mass spectral measurements. Thus, when the concentration of the compound in the source with respect to the reactant gas is increased, the formation of $[\text{M}_2\text{H}]^+$ ions is favoured. In the case of tertiary alcohols, this type of ions is more stable than the ion MH^+ as long as the attractive effect of the proton can be shared between the two hydroxyls.

The mass spectrum of (1) obtained under these conditions shows a peak $[\text{M}_2\text{H}]^+$ at m/e 481 proving its molecular weight 240. Similarly, the mass spectral

measurement in presence of an excess of a glycol (G) of known structure results in the formation of $[\text{MGH}]^+$ ions. The spectrum of balanitol measured in presence of 1,6-hexanediol (m/e 118) displays a significant peak $[\text{MGH}]^+$ at m/e 359 along with that at m/e 223 $[\text{MH}-18]^+$. Also, the use of ammonia as a reactant gas, the proton affinity of which is higher than that of alcohols, may also be helpful in the determination of the molecular weight. Thus, the chemical ionisation mass spectrum of balanitol obtained in presence of ammonia displays strong peaks $[\text{MNH}_4]^+$ at m/e 258 and $[\text{MNH}_4\text{NH}_3]^+$ at m/e 275, the former being the base peak in the spectrum.

Based on the arguments presented above structure 1 is proposed for balanitol.

The second isolate, compound B, m.p. 78-79°, $[\alpha]_D = -27.9^\circ$, gave elemental analysis and mass spectral data for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$ $[\text{M}^+-18]$. Its IR spectrum indicated the presence of hydroxyl bands and its $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum disclosed signals for secondary methyl (0.92 ppm; $J=6$ Hz), tertiary methyl (1.03 ppm) and gem-dimethyl of a hydroxyisopropyl group (1.07 ppm). Compound B failed to yield an oxidation or acetylation product. The single frequency decoupled ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound B disclosed two singlets at 73.92 and 74.5 ppm indicating the presence of two tertiary alcohols in the molecule. Further chemical analysis of compound B was precluded due to paucity of material.

Experimental

Melting points were determined using a Kofler hot-stage microscope and are uncorrected. Optical rotations were determined at room temp. on a Roussel-Jouan "Quick polarimeter". Electron impact mass spectra were taken on a MS 50-AEI Spectrometer and chemical ionisation spectra on a modified MS 9-AEI²³. The $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra were recorded on a Varian A60 or T60 spectrometer in deuteriochloroform using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Noise and single frequency decoupled $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 solution on a Bruker HX-90E F.T. NMR Spectrometer operating at 22.63 MHz.

Isolation of compounds A and B The ground bark of *Balanites roxburghii* (500 g) was extracted successively with hexane and with chloroform. Removal of the solvents left yellow residues 8.2 g and 3.8 g, respectively. The chloroform extract was taken in ether and the ether-soluble product (2.2 g) was chromatographed over silica gel column using chloroform containing increasing amounts of methanol to yield compounds A and B.

Compound A-balanitol (1). Crystals from benzene, m.p. 158-160°, $[\alpha]_D = +10.8^\circ$ ($c=0.835$; CHCl_3). MS: very weak peak at m/e 240 (M^+) small peak at m/e 225 (M^+-15) and a strong peak at m/e 182 ($\text{M}^+-\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}$). Found: C, 74.93; H, 11.49%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$: C, 74.95; H, 11.73%.

Hydroxy ketone (2). Balanitol (110 mg) was dissolved in acetone (3 ml) and Jones' reagent was added dropwise with cooling till persistence of the yellow color. After 30 min. at room temp. a few drops of methanol were added to destroy the excess of the reagent. The product, isolated in the usual manner, was purified by column chromatography on silicic acid. A mixture of benzene-ether (3:1) eluted 70 mg of viscous liquid that crystallized from hexane as colourless needles, m.p. 101-103° $[\alpha]_D = +50.5$ ($c=0.81$; CHCl_3). MS: peak at m/e 238 (M^+), m/e 223 (M^+-15) and base peak at m/e 180 ($\text{M}^+-\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}$). Found: C, 75.53; H, 10.86%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2$: C, 75.58; H, 11.00%.

Deuteration of 2 has been performed by heating 2 (80 mg) in 1 ml CD_3OD containing two drops of D_2O in presence of sodium. After refluxing for 1 hr., the mixture was diluted with D_2O , acidified with acetic acid and extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed with D_2O , dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent distilled off. Crystallisation from hexane gave di-deuterio-hydroxyketone 2. MS: peak at m/e 240 (M^+), m/e 225 (M^+-15) and peak at m/e 182 ($\text{M}^+-\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}$).

Conversion of 2 to dihydroeudesmol (3).—To a solution of compound 2 (46 mg) in methanol (1 ml) tosylhydrazide (70 mg) was added. The mixture was heated to reflux for 1 hr. and kept then at room temp. for 3 hr. Water was added and the product was extracted with ether to yield the corresponding tosylhydrazone

TABLE—CARBON CHEMICAL SHIFTS*

	1	2	3	4	5
C-1	80.3	216.0	41.7	38.0	41.9 ^a
C-2	27.3 ^a	34.0	17.5	23.0	23.5
C-3	31.5 ^b	32.6 ^a	33.8	121.0	36.9
C-4	33.1 ^b	32.3 ^a	33.8	135.2	151.0
C-5	45.9 ^c	47.0 ^b	47.1 ^a	46.7 ^a	49.5 ^b
C-6	26.4 ^a	26.8	28.2	24.4	25.1
C-7	49.7 ^c	49.2 ^b	50.2 ^a	49.9 ^a	49.9 ^b
C-8	22.6	22.3	22.8	22.5	22.4
C-9	40.3	35.1	44.6	40.2	41.2 ^a
C-10	39.2	48.2	33.8	32.2	35.9
C-11	72.5	72.4	72.6	72.9	72.8
C-12	27.3	27.5	27.3	27.2	27.2
C-13	26.9	26.8	27.0	27.2	27.2
C-14	14.9	14.8	14.8	21.2	105.3
C-15	14.0	19.2	19.6	15.6	16.3

*The δ values are in parts per million downfield from Me_4Si . a-c Signals within any vertical column may be reversed.

(78 mg), homogeneous on TLC. To a solution of the latter in methanol (4 ml), NaBH_4 (70 mg) was portion-wise added and the mixture refluxed for 2 hr. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After the usual workup, the crude product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (elution with benzene-ether, 95 : 5) to yield dihydro-eudesmol (3), m.p. (after sublimation) $85-86^\circ[\alpha]_D^{20} = +19^\circ (c=0.66; \text{CHCl}_3)$. It was identical with the sample obtained by hydrogenation of β -eudesmol (Co-TLC, m.p., MS, $^1\text{H-NMR}$).

β -Eudesmol (5). A 6:10 mixture of α - and β -eudesmol (300 mg) in benzene (16 ml) was irradiated in a quartz tube by a mercury-vapour lamp for 82 hr. The isomerisation reaction was monitored by $^1\text{H-NMR}$. The recovered material, in ether, was washed with *N* NaOH solution and then with water. The product was purified by column chromatography on alumina. Elution with petrol-ether/ether (1:1) gave pure β -eudesmol(5)⁴ $^1\text{H-NMR}$: δ 0.66 ppm (3H, s, angular-Me), 1.19 ppm [6H, s, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{-C-OH}$], signals at 4.45 and 4.7 ppm (1 H each, $\text{CH}_2 = \text{C}$).

Dihydroeudesmol (3). — β -Eudesmol 5 (60 mg) in ethylacetate containing Adams catalyse (25 mg) was hydrogenated for 3 hr. at room temp. and atm. pressure. The isolated product was chromatographed on silica gel to give 3, m.p. $85-86^\circ$. MS : *m/e* 209 ($\text{M}^+ - 15$), *m/e* 151.

Dioxolane 6. — To a solution of compound 2 (30 mg) in dry benzene (20 ml), ethylene glycol (0.15 ml) and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (10 mg) were added ; the mixture was heated to reflux with continuous removal of water (Dean-Starck trap) for 2 hr. After the usual work-up, the crude product was chromatographed on silica gel to yield the dioxolane 6 (mixture of double band isomers). IR : no absorption in the OH and CO region.

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